

transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily
vanilloid (V) member 6 or epithelial calcium channel 2
(TRPV6 / ECAC2 / CAT1) : Machine learning discoveries
of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : TRPV6 is a membrane Ca²⁺ channel protein belonging to the transient receptor potential family (TRP) of proteins. They are channel proteins critical for ionic homeostasis and the perception of various physical and chemical stimuli. It is implicated in Ca transport in the kidney, prostatic carcinoma, breast adenocarcinoma, renal calcium stone patients, myeloid leukemia, pseudohypoaldosteronism type II, bone homeostasis, Oculocerebrorenal syndrome of Lowe, non-small-cell lung cancer, parathyroid glands, cystic fibrosis, esophageal squamous cell carcinoma, transient neonatal hyperparathyroidism, cardiomyocytes, chronic pancreatitis and ulcerative colitis, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of TRPV6, some of which have been known to exist via

*ML dicoveries of TRPV6 synergy in Meningiomas

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wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: TRPV6, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6)

Stevens and Vo [13] investigated the potential induction of cationic and zwitterionic amino acid transport systems and mRNA transcripts in primary neuronal cultures from rat hypothalamus/brainstem. They assessed cultures exposed to bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) plus interferon- γ (IFN γ) with respect to northern blot analyses, L-leucine/L-arginine cross-inhibition uptake profiles in the presence and absence of Na⁺, and initial rate sodium-independent L-arginine transport kinetics. They observed that L-Arginine uptake activity was constitutively expressed along with uninduced steady-state levels of CAT1 and 4F2hc transcripts. Their data were consistent with L-arginine membrane uptake occurring via only system y⁺ encoded by constitutive CAT1, with possible physiologic contribution by constitutive 4F2hc transcripts in primary neuronal cultures.

Calcium is a major component of the mineral phase of bone and serves as a key intracellular second messenger. Postnatally, all bodily calcium must be absorbed from the diet through the intestine. Peng et al. [14] reported the properties of CAT1, which they cloned from rat duodenum using an expression cloning strategy in *Xenopus laevis* oocytes, which likely played a key role in the intestinal uptake of calcium. They found that CAT1 showed homology (75% amino acid sequence identity) to the apical calcium channel ECAC, which was cloned from vitamin D-responsive cells of rabbit kidney and was structurally related to the capsaicin receptor and the TRP family of ion channels. In rat tissues, they found the presence of a 3-kilobase CAT1 transcript in duodenum, proximal jejunum, cecum, and colon, and a 6.5-kilobase transcript in brain, thymus, and adrenal gland. Their in-situ hybridization revealed strong CAT1 mRNA expression in enterocytes of duodenum, proximal jejunum, and cecum. When expressed in *Xenopus* oocytes, they observed that CAT1 mediated saturable Ca²⁺ uptake with a Michaelis constant of 0.44 mM. Transport of Ca²⁺ by CAT1 was electrogenic, voltage-dependent, and exhibits a charge/Ca²⁺ uptake ratio close to 2:1, indicating that CAT1-mediated Ca²⁺ influx was not coupled to other ions. CAT1 is also permeant to Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺ (but not Mg²⁺), although the currents evoked by Sr²⁺ and Ba²⁺ were much smaller than those evoked by Ca²⁺. The trivalent cations Gd³⁺ and La³⁺ and the divalent cations Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Co²⁺, and Ni²⁺ (each at 100 microM) did not evoke currents themselves, but inhibited CAT1-mediated Ca²⁺ transport. Their studies suggested that CAT1 provided the principal mechanism for Ca²⁺ entry into enterocytes as part of the transcellular pathway of calcium absorption in the intestine.

Transcellular calcium transport occurs in many epithelial tissues including intestine, kidney, and placenta. Peng et al. [15] identified the human ortholog (hCAT1) of the cloned rat CAT1, that mediated intestinal calcium uptake. The observed presence of hCAT1 messenger RNA in the gastrointestinal tract, including esophagus, stomach, duodenum, jejunum, ileum, and colon and high levels of hCAT1 transcripts in pancreas, placenta, prostate, and salivary gland, while moderate levels in liver, kidney, and testis. It was assigned to the long arm of chromosome 7, bands q33-34. They also found that hCAT1 expression in *Xenopus laevis* oocytes, promoted saturable Ca²⁺ uptake with a Michaelis constant of 0.25 mM.

Calcium absorption in intestine and kidney involves transport through the apical membrane, cytoplasm, and basolateral membrane of the epithelial cells. Apical mem-

brane calcium influx channels had been described in rabbit (epithelial calcium channel, ECAC) and rat CAT1. Barley et al. [16] amplified from human duodenum a 446-base partial cDNA probe (ECAC2) having a predicted amino acid similarity of 97% to rat CAT1. Their data showed that although individual variations in calcium channel transcripts are not vitamin D dependent, expression of genes governing apical entry and basolateral extrusion are tightly linked. This might account for some of the unexplained variability in calcium absorption.

1.3. Roles of TRPV6 in different disease

Suzuki et al. [17] investigated the molecular mechanism of **Ca transport in the kidney**, and isolated Ca-permeable channels, rECAC (rat ECAC) and mCAT (mouse CAT1), from rodent kidney, which are recently reported as Ca-transporting proteins. RT-PCR suggested the presence of CAT1 in medullary tubules. It showed 67% homology with rECAC constructing a family. They concluded that ECAC and CaT are a molecular family of ion channel with similar characteristics, contributing Ca transport in the kidney.

Ca²⁺ signaling is important for growth and survival of **prostatic carcinoma** (PCa) cells. Peng et al. [18] reported that CAT1 was expressed at high levels in human PCa and in the LNCaP PCa cell line. They observed elevated levels of CAT1 mRNA in PCa specimens in comparison to benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) specimens and positively correlated with Gleason grade in a PCa series. Further, CAT1 mRNA was suppressed by androgen and was induced by a specific androgen receptor antagonist in LNCaP cells. In a first, their findings implicated a Ca²⁺ channel in PCa progression and suggested that CAT1 might be a novel target for therapy.

TRPV6 is an endothelial calcium entry channel that is strongly expressed in **breast adenocarcinoma** tissue. Bolanz et al. [19] further confirmed this observation by analysis of breast cancer tissues, which indicated that TRPV6 mRNA expression was up-regulated between 2-fold and 15-fold compared with the average in normal breast tissue. Interestingly, the estrogen receptor antagonist tamoxifen reduced expression of TRPV6 and is able to inhibit its calcium transport activity (IC₅₀, 7.5 μmol/L). Their in vitro model showed that TRPV6 could be regulated by estrogen, progesterone, tamoxifen, and 1,25-vitamin D and has a large influence on breast cancer cell proliferation. Moreover, the effect of tamoxifen on cell viability was enhanced when TRPV6 expression was silenced with small interfering RNA. Thus they hypothesized that TRPV6 might be a novel target for the development of calcium channel inhibitors to treat breast adenocarcinoma expressing TRPV6.

The TRPV6 gene was completely sequenced in 170 **renal calcium stone patients**, by Suzuki et al. [20]. The frequency of an ancestral TRPV6 haplotype consisting of three non-synonymous polymorphisms (C157R, M378V, M681T) was significantly higher (P = 0.039) in calcium stone formers (8.4%; derived = 502, ancestral = 46) compared to non-stone-forming individuals (5.4%; derived = 645, ancestral = 37). Their results suggested that the ancestral gain-of-function haplotype in TRPV6 played a role in calcium stone formation in certain forms of absorptive hypercalciuria.

In blood cells, changes in intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration ([Ca²⁺]_i) are associated with multiple cellular events, including activation of cellular kinases and phos-

phatases, degranulation, regulation of cytoskeleton binding proteins, transcriptional control, and modulation of surface receptors. Semenova et al. [21] showed that human leukemia K562 cells endogenously coexpressed TRPV-5/6 mRNAs and further demonstrated that TRPV-5/6 channel proteins were present in both the total lysates and the crude membrane preparations from leukemia cells. Their single-channel patch-clamp experiments demonstrated the presence of inwardly rectifying monovalent currents that displayed kinetic characteristics of unitary TRPV5 and/or TRPV6 currents and were blocked by extracellular Ca^{2+} and ruthenium red. Thus their data strongly indicated that human **myeloid leukemia** cells coexpressed functional TRPV5 and TRPV6 calcium channels that might interact with each other and contribute into intracellular Ca^{2+} signaling.

The mechanisms underlying hypercalciuria in **pseudohypoaldosteronism type II** (PHAII) caused by WNK4 mutations had remained unclear and Yang et al. [22] used $\text{Wnk4}^{D561A/+}$ knock-in mice as a model of human PHAII for investigating the pathogenesis of hypercalciuria in PHAII. For this, serum and urine biochemistries were obtained from $\text{Wnk4}^{+/+}$ and $\text{Wnk4}^{D561A/+}$ littermates. The observed that compared with $\text{Wnk4}^{+/+}$ littermate controls, $\text{Wnk4}^{D561A/+}$ mice manifested hypercalciuria despite no significant differences in serum creatinine, ionized Ca^{2+} , PTH, and 1,25 hydroxylvitamin D(3) levels. Also, there was no significant difference in TRPV5 expression, but a significant increase in TRPV6 and CBP-D28k was observed in $\text{Wnk4}^{D561A/+}$ mice. They hypothesized that decreased Ca^{2+} reabsorption in the upstream nephron, especially in the thick ascending loops of Henle, with a secondary adaptive increase in TRPV6 and CBP-D28k expression in the distal tubules might be involved in the hypercalciuria of PHAII.

Energy-dependent intestinal calcium absorption is important for the maintenance of calcium and **bone homeostasis**, especially when dietary calcium supply is restricted. The active form of vitamin D, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ [1,25(OH)₂D₃], is a crucial regulator of this process and increases the expression of TRPV6 calcium channel that mediates calcium transfer across the intestinal apical membrane. Lieben et al. [23] thoroughly analyzed the bone phenotype of TRPV6^{-/-} mice receiving a normal (approximately 1%) or low (approximately 0.02%) calcium diet from weaning onwards. When dietary supply of calcium was normal, TRPV6 inactivation did not affect growth plate morphology, bone mass and remodeling parameters in young adult or aging mice; On the contrary, restricting dietary calcium had no effect on serum calcium levels and resulted in a comparable reduction in bone mass accrual in TRPV6^{+/+} and TRPV6^{-/-} mice (-35% and 45% respectively). This decrease in bone mass was associated with a similar increase in bone resorption, whereas serum osteocalcin levels and the amount of unmineralized bone matrix were only significantly increased in TRPV6^{-/-} mice. Their findings indicated that TRPV6 contributed to intestinal calcium transport when dietary calcium supply is limited, which indirectly regulated bone formation and/or mineralization.

Oculocerebrorenal syndrome of Lowe (OCRL) gene product is a phosphatidyl inositol 4,5-bisphosphate [PI(4,5)P₂] 5-phosphatase, and mutations of OCRL cause Lowe syndrome and Dent disease, both of which are frequently associated with hypercalciuria. Hyperabsorption of Ca^{2+} was found in patients of Dent disease with increased Ca^{2+} excretion. Wu et al. [24] tested whether TRPV6 was regulated by

OCRL and, if so, to what extent it was altered by Dent-causing OCRL mutations. They observed that exogenous OCRL decreased TRPV6-mediated Ca^{2+} uptake by regulating the function and trafficking of TRPV6 through different domains of OCRL. They also found that the $\text{PI}(4,5)\text{P}_2$ 5-phosphatase domain suppressed the TRPV6-mediated Ca^{2+} transport likely through regulating the $\text{PI}(4,5)\text{P}_2$ level needed for TRPV6 function without affecting TRPV6 protein abundance of TRPV6 at the cell surface. The forward trafficking of TRPV6 was decreased by OCRL. Further, knocking down endogenous *X. laevis* OCRL by antisense approach increased TRPV6-mediated Ca^{2+} transport and TRPV6 forward trafficking. On examining all seven Dent-causing OCRL mutations, it was found that there was evasion of the inhibitory effect on TRPV6-mediated Ca^{2+} transport together with decreased overall $\text{PI}(4,5)\text{P}_2$ 5-phosphatase activity. They concluded that OCRL suppressed TRPV6 via two separate mechanisms.

Fan et al. [25] investigated the expression of epithelial Ca^{2+} channel transient receptor TRPV-5/6 in **non-small-cell lung cancer** (NSCLC) and assessed their prognostic role in patients after surgical resection. They observed strong protein expression (grade *geq* 2) of TRPV-5/6 using IHC, among the 145 patients who had undergone surgical resection of NSCLCs, in a lower percentage of primary tumor tissues than in non-tumor tissues of same patients. Decreased expression of TRPV-5/6 in tumor tissues was observed in NSCLC patients and was associated with shorter median survival time after surgical resection. Combined expression of TRPV-5/6 in tumor tissues demonstrated promising prognostic value in NSCLC patients.

The parathyroid glands play an overall regulatory role in the systemic Ca^{2+} homeostasis. In a first, Giusti et al. [26] demonstrated the presence of the Ca^{2+} channels transient receptor TRPV-5/6 in human **parathyroid glands**. TRPV-5/6 transcripts were then identified both in normal and pathological tissues and predominant immunoreactive bands were detected at 75-80 kD for both vanilloid channels. Further, they observed that these channels co-localized with the calcium-sensing receptor (CASR) on the membrane surface, but immunoreactivity was also detected in the cytosol and around the nuclei. Their data showed that an increase of protein expression of both TRPV-5/6 was recorded in adenoma samples compared with normal glands. This suggested a potential relation with the cell calcium signalling pathway and the pathological processes of these glands.

Increase of Ca^{2+} influx in **Cystic Fibrosis** (CF) cells has been reported to be related to Transient Receptor Potential Canonical (TRPC6) channel, which is implicated in a functional coupling with Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane conductance Regulator (CFTR). Vachel et al. [27] investigated the involvement of TRPV-5/6 in Ca^{2+} influx in CF and non-CF human bronchial epithelial cell lines. For this, they used 16HBE14o-, CFBE41o- cell lines, primary human airway epithelial cells (hAEC) and freshly isolated human airway epithelial cells from CF and non-CF individuals. They showed that both channels were expressed in CF and non-CF cells and constitutive Ca^{2+} influx was significantly higher (85%) in cells from CF individuals compared to cells from non-CF ones. Using the selective inhibitor of TRPV6 channel SOR-C27 and a siRNA strategy, their results revealed that TRPV6 was mostly involved in the increase of Ca^{2+} influx. Further, TRPV6 channel was negatively regulated by the PLC-PIP2 pathway. Their study revealed TRPV6 and PLC- δ 1 as critical actor of Ca^{2+} homeostasis in CF human bronchial epithelial cells.

Zhang et al. [28] tried to elucidate the role of TRPV6 in predicting prognosis of patients with **esophageal squamous cell carcinoma** (ESCC) and found that TRPV6 was down-regulated in ESCC. As a predictive biomarker, TRPV6 plays a Janus-like role in predicting survival of male and female ESCC patients.

Transient neonatal hyperparathyroidism (TNHP) is etiologically a heterogeneous condition and one of the etiologies is an insufficient maternal-fetal calcium transport through the placenta. Suzuki et al. [29] reported six subjects with homozygous and/or compound-heterozygous mutations in TRPV6. They identified three missense variants (at the outer edges of the second and third transmembrane domains) that alter the localization of the TRPV6 - one recurrent variant at the S2-S3 loop and two recurrent variants (in the fourth ankyrin repeat domain) that impair TRPV6 stability. Further, Compound heterozygous loss-of-function mutations for the pathogenic frameshift allele and the allele with an intronic c.607+5G>A mutation resulted in the most severe phenotype. Their results suggested that TNHP is an autosomal-recessive disease caused by TRPV6 mutations that affect maternal-fetal calcium transport.

Li et al. [30] hypothesized that ER stress might upregulate the expression of TRPV6, which in turn served to protect human embryonic stem cell-derived **cardiomyocytes** (hESC-CMs) from endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress-induced apoptotic cell death. They found that ER stress induced by thapsigargin and tunicamycin led to increased expression of TRPV6 via ATF6 α signaling branch, while siRNA-mediated knockdown of TRPV6 aggravated ER stress-induced apoptotic cell death, whereas overexpression of TRPV6 attenuated ER stress-induced apoptosis in hESC-CMs. Their results provided strong evidence that, under ER stress, TRPV6 was upregulated to protect hESC-CMs from apoptotic cell death via ATF6 α -TRPV6-JNK pathway.

Changes in pancreatic calcium levels affect secretion and might be involved in development of **chronic pancreatitis** (CP). Masamune et al. [31] investigated the association of CP with TRPV6 in an international cohort of patients and in mice. For this, they performed whole-exome DNA sequencing from a patient with idiopathic CP and from his parents, who did not have CP. Further, they validated their findings by sequencing DNA from 300 patients with CP (not associated with alcohol consumption) and 1070 persons from the general population in Japan (control individuals). In replication studies, they sequenced DNA from patients with early-onset CP (20 years or younger) not associated with alcohol consumption from France (n = 470) and Germany (n = 410). They found that patients with early-onset CP not associated with alcohol consumption carry variants in TRPV6 that affect the function of its product, perhaps by altering Ca²⁺ balance in pancreatic cells. They concluded that TRPV6 regulated Ca²⁺ homeostasis and pancreatic inflammation.

TRPV subfamily is involved in the development of gastrointestinal diseases such as **ulcerative colitis** (UC). Toledo Mauriño et al. [32] aimed to characterize the gene and protein expression of the TRPV subfamily in UC patients and controls. They found the gene expression of TRPV6 significantly higher in the colonic tissue from patients with active UC compared with the control group and TRPV6 was upregulated in all intestinal layers from the UC patients vs controls.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations

via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [33] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [34] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [34].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [35]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [36], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [33] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM^{Rank}_{classify}$ Joachims [33]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [37], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")` • use `source("manuscript-2-2.R")` • use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. TRPV6 related synergies

Note - TRPV6 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of TRPV6 were recorded.

3.1.1. TRPV6 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with TRPV6 showed high rankings - USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), tolloid like 1 (TLL1), mucolipin TRP cation channel 3 (MCOLN3), erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 3 (ERBB3), ST6 N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 2 (ST6GALNAC2), ribosomal protein S6 kinase A6 (RPS6KA6), calpain 6 (CAPN6), ATP binding cassette subfamily B member 1 (ABCB1), tolloid like 2 (TLL2), apolipoprotein L4 (APOL4), neurotensin receptor 1 (NTSR1), mesothelin (MSLN), junctophilin 1 (JPH1), neurocalcin delta (NCALD), tight junction protein 3 (TJP3), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), FA complementation group E (FANCE), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), melanophilin (MLPH), 24-dehydrocholesterol reductase (DHCR24), tetraspanin 1 (TSPAN1), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), lecithin retinol acyltransferase (LRAT), citron rho-interacting serine/threonine kinase (CIT), ATPase phospholipid transporting 8A1 (ATP8A1), myelin regulatory factor (MYRF), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 4 (PEL blood group) (ABCC4), SRY-box transcription factor 9 (SOX9), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 2 (PCSK2), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 2 (HSPA2), kallikrein related peptidase 10 (KLK10), kallikrein related peptidase 8 (KLK8), proline rich and Gla domain 3 (PRRG3), microtubule associated scaffold protein 2 (MTUS2), LARGE xylosyl- and glucuronyltransferase 1 (LARGE1), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 9 (TTC9), BICD family like cargo adaptor 1 (BICDL1), epidermal growth factor (EGF), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), immunoglobulin like domain containing receptor 2 (ILDR2), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), HHIP like 2 (HHIPL2),

polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), glutamate decarboxylase like 1 (GADL1), solute carrier family 26 member 7 (SLC26A7), lipocalin 2 (LCN2), cadherin 8 (CDH8), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), chondrolectin (CHODL), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), carboxypeptidase A3 (CPA3), neuropeptide Y receptor Y1 (NPY1R), hyperpolarization activated cyclic nucleotide gated potassium channel 1 (HCN1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), solute carrier family 16 member 9 (SLC16A9), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), myosin IA (MYO1A), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), RAB3B, member RAS oncogene family (RAB3B), heparan sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 2 (HS6ST2), CDC42 binding protein kinase gamma (CDC42BPG), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), angiopoietin like 7 (ANGPTL7), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), radial spoke head component 9 (RSPH9), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), solute carrier family 35 member G1 (SLC35G1), myosin ID (MYO1D), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1), synemin (SYNM), family with sequence similarity 162 member B (FAM162B), oxysterol binding protein 2 (OSBP2), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), transcobalamin 2 (TCN2), insulin induced gene 1 (INSIG1), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), phospholipase A2 group IIA (PLA2G2A), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), laminin subunit beta 3 (LAMB3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2) and SEC14 like lipid binding 6 (SEC14L6).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of TRPV6 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t TRPV6 with TRPV6 – > USH1C / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ERBB3 / ST6GALNAC2 / RPS6KA6 / CAPN6 / ABCB1 / TLL2 / APOL4 / NTSR1 / MSLN / JPH1 / NCALD / TJP3 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B / COBL / FANCE / IL1RL1 / MLPH / DHCR24 / TSPAN1 / PLPPR4 / LRAT / CIT / ATP8A1 / MYRF / ABCC4 / SOX9 / PCSK2 / HSPA2 / KLK10 / KLK8 / PRRG3 / MTUS2 / LARGE1 / TTC9 / BICDL1 / EGF / MDGA2 / MAEL / ILDR2 / SUSD4 / HHIPL2 / GALNT13 / GADL1 / SLC26A7 / LCN2 / CDH8 / CCDC3 / CHOD / FBXO32 / COX6B / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / DEFB1 / PHYHIPL / SLC16A9 / PPP1R3 / CACNB2 / SCN3B / PLEKHA7 / MYO1A / SGSM1 / BDKRB2 / RAB3B / HS6ST2 / CDC42BPG /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TRPV6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TRPV6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USH1C - TRPV6	208	15	207	199	TLL1 - TRPV6	241	33	259	171
MCOLN3 - TRPV6	273	101	226	204	ERBB3 - TRPV6	217	16	289	224
ST6GALNAC2 - TRPV6	157	208	192	166	RPS6KA6 - TRPV6	181	47	262	294
CAPN6 - TRPV6	289	221	178	216	ABCB1 - TRPV6	219	51	277	200
TLL2 - TRPV6	302	150	258	229	APOL4 - TRPV6	240	31	167	297
NTSR1 - TRPV6	250	138	247	196	MSLN - TRPV6	172	35	253	176
JPH1 - TRPV6	275	23	205	165	NCALD - TRPV6	255	55	284	263
TJP3 - TRPV6	206	98	248	249	GRIK5 - TRPV6	282	273	229	279
RUNDC3B - TRPV6	151	56	193	275	COBL - TRPV6	232	10	224	227
FANCE - TRPV6	39	159	181	283	IL1RL1 - TRPV6	222	4	283	153
MLPH - TRPV6	274	76	246	158	DHCR24 - TRPV6	163	6	203	277
TSPAN1 - TRPV6	198	116	273	232	PLPPR4 - TRPV6	244	137	218	173
LRAT - TRPV6	166	231	206	44	CIT - TRPV6	141	153	166	280
ATP8A1 - TRPV6	171	161	204	3	MYRF - TRPV6	197	69	268	175
ABCC4 - TRPV6	178	181	154	17	SOX9 - TRPV6	268	169	240	178
PCSK2 - TRPV6	285	68	293	203	HSPA2 - TRPV6	165	203	158	272
KLK10 - TRPV6	236	79	230	256	KLK8 - TRPV6	200	41	288	225
PRRG3 - TRPV6	254	94	300	150	MTUS2 - TRPV6	263	14	266	240
LARGE1 - TRPV6	216	280	209	64	TTC9 - TRPV6	40	230	155	268
BICDL1 - TRPV6	205	1	187	180	EGF - TRPV6	193	270	133	262
MDGA2 - TRPV6	182	88	303	186	MAEL - TRPV6	257	20	274	192
ILDR2 - TRPV6	270	11	305	157	SUSD4 - TRPV6	207	134	197	162
HHIPL2 - TRPV6	204	65	234	214	GALNT13 - TRPV6	174	62	188	155
GADL1 - TRPV6	201	29	297	183	SLC26A7 - TRPV6	284	39	279	205
LCN2 - TRPV6	153	61	199	273	CDH8 - TRPV6	223	53	298	255

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between TRPV6 VS Individual members.

ANO5 / ANGPTL / MBOAT1 / SPTLC3 / CSDC2 / RSPH9 / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 / MYO1D / LRRN4CL / ERN1 / WSCD1 / SYNM / FAM162B / OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / TCN2 / INSIG1 / NF2 / BCR / PLA2G2A / FAM78B / FAT4 / SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / SREBF2 / SEC14L6.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic TRPV6 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of TRPV6-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS TRPV6									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T TRPV6									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CCDC3 - TRPV6	115	172	275	209	CHODL - TRPV6	237	12	276	202
FBXO32 - TRPV6	192	205	269	228	COX6B2 - TRPV6	243	54	306	161
CPA3 - TRPV6	234	131	290	160	NPY1R - TRPV6	191	209	301	236
HCN1 - TRPV6	235	24	245	168	DEFB1 - TRPV6	307	60	271	156
PHYHIPL - TRPV6	260	171	165	289	SLC16A9 - TRPV6	188	250	190	251
PPP1R36 - TRPV6	211	227	194	290	CACNB2 - TRPV6	267	254	260	60
SCN3B - TRPV6	297	192	282	11	PLEKHA7 - TRPV6	304	163	291	193
MYO1A - TRPV6	228	180	98	299	SGSM1 - TRPV6	281	50	237	223
BDKRB2 - TRPV6	196	240	70	151	RAB3B - TRPV6	280	297	168	13
HS6ST2 - TRPV6	226	224	39	245	CDC42BPG - TRPV6	295	165	225	252
ANO5 - TRPV6	239	214	107	174	ANGPTL7 - TRPV6	290	222	55	295
MBOAT1 - TRPV6	231	84	210	291	SPTLC3 - TRPV6	266	73	285	253
CSDC2 - TRPV6	261	259	120	231	RSPH9 - TRPV6	179	258	238	8
SLCO2A1 - TRPV6	164	255	196	12	SLC35G1 - TRPV6	278	18	264	246
MYO1D - TRPV6	227	196	251	112	LRRN4CL - TRPV6	225	281	242	287
ERN1 - TRPV6	291	17	292	164	WSCD1 - TRPV6	249	223	265	218
SYNM - TRPV6	253	253	176	286	FAM162B - TRPV6	224	303	19	217
OSBP2 - TRPV6	233	225	35	243	SDR42E1 - TRPV6	183	213	153	188
MAFF - TRPV6	245	142	228	303	RBM11 - TRPV6	248	160	101	298
TCN2 - TRPV6	186	216	243	40	INSIG1 - TRPV6	296	154	286	211
NF2 - TRPV6	247	187	302	306	BCR - TRPV6	286	194	213	34
PLA2G2A - TRPV6	159	265	33	167	FAM78B - TRPV6	279	232	222	169
FAT4 - TRPV6	271	112	191	296	SLC6A9 - TRPV6	252	70	219	241
LAMB3 - TRPV6	213	178	183	21	ENPP1 - TRPV6	242	184	81	307
AFDN-DT - TRPV6	299	34	235	235	SH3BGRL2 - TRPV6	189	67	254	197
SREBF2 - TRPV6	288	37	150	247	SEC14L6 - TRPV6	52	235	171	194

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between TRPV6 VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t TRPV6	
USH1C / TLL1 / MCOLN3 / ERBB3 / ST6GALNAC2 ...	
RPS6KA6 / CAPN6 / ABCB1 / TLL2 / APOL4 / NTSR1 ...	
MSLN / JPH1 / NCALD / TJP3 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B ...	
COBL / FANCE / IL1RL1 / MLPH / DHCR24 / TSPAN1 ...	
PLPPR4 / LRAT / CIT / ATP8A1 / MYRF / ABCC4 ...	
SOX9 / PCSK2 / HSPA2 / KLK10 / KLK8 / PRRG3 ...	
MTUS2 / LARGE1 / TTC9 / BICDL1 / EGF / MDGA2 ...	
MAEL / ILDR2 / SUSD4 / HHIPL2 / GALNT13 / GADL1 ...	
SLC26A7 / LCN2 / CDH8 / CCDC3 / CHOD / FBXO32 ...	
COX6B / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 / DEFB1 / PHYHIPL ...	
SLC16A9 / PPP1R3 / CACNB2 / SCN3B / PLEKHA7 / MYO1A ...	
SGSM1 / BDKRB2 / RAB3B / HS6ST2 / CDC42BPG / ANO5 ...	
ANGPTL / MBOAT1 / SPTLC3 / CSDC2 / RSPH9 / SLCO2A1 ...	
SLC35G1 / MYO1D / LRRN4CL / ERN1 / WSCD1 / SYNM ...	
FAM162B / OSBP2 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / TCN2 ...	
INSIG1 / NF2 / BCR / PLA2G2A / FAM78B / FAT4 ...	
SLC6A9 / LAMB3 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 ...	
SREBF2 / SEC14L6	TRPV6

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between TRPV6 and Individual members.

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